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LS-SVM IMPROVEMENT USING PSO AND GWO TO DETERMINE FLASHOVER VOLTAGE OF POLLUTED INSULATORS

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Abstract – The electricity system's dependability is determined mainly by environmental and meteorological conditions, which create flashovers on dirty insulators, resulting in system outages. The buildup of airborne pollutants owing to natural, industrial, or even combined pollution during the dry weather period and their subsequent soaking, mainly by high humidity, is a severe concern for insulating systems. This issue motivated the creation of a test station that conducts laboratory experiments on intentionally contaminated insulators. Several investigations into the performance of insulators in polluted environments have been completed, with mathematical or physical models being used, tests being performed, and simulation programs being developed. This work endeavors to explain the possibilities of a mixture model between Machine Learning (ML) in light of least-squares support vector machine (LS-SVM) and Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO) and Grey Wolf optimizer (GWO) in high voltage applications. Next, we have developed the LS-SVM-PSO and LSSVM-GWO models to provide a non-linear relationship between the insulator properties and the critical voltage. The data used to train and test the model comes from experimental measurements and a mathematical model. A comparison of several approaches—ANN, ANFIS, and Fuzzy Logic (FL)—demonstrates the accuracy and goodness of LS-SVM with PSO and LS-SVM with GWO. Furthermore, LS-SVM with GWO and LSSVM with PSO provides a reasonable estimation of outcomes that are confirmed by experimental experiments.

Keywords – High voltage insulators, flashover voltage, polluted insulator, Least squares support vector machine(LSSVM), Grey Wolf optimizer (GWO), Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO).

I. INTRODUCTION

Outdoor high-voltage insulators are critical components of transmission lines. Pollution is one of their primary restrictions [1] [2]. The pollution enables a modest leakage current to flow in dry conditions, but in the presence of light rain, fog, or dew, the surface becomes extremely conductive, potentially leading to a flashover [3]. The reason for this is that when pollution gets moist, its presence causes an increase in leakage current as well as a widening of the dry band. As a result, it is possible to claim that the flashover phenomena caused by insulator contamination follow a well-

defined process. The first is the deposition of pollutants on the insulator's surface. Second, the dirty surface becomes moistened. Thirdly, the value of the leakage current will grow. Lastly, the flashover expresses itself along the insulator's surface through contaminated patches [4].

The insulator's surface properties may alter with time and under certain circumstances, potentially leading to premature aging [5]. The critical flashover voltage of a contaminated insulator is an important characteristic for power system dependability. Several methods for estimating the flashover voltage have been devised.

Experimentation takes time and adds to the cost of the system. To address this issue, high voltage engineering research groups presented certain mathematical models based on physical modeling, employing electrical equivalent models, or mathematical regressions using artificial intelligence approximates [6] [7]. The quantity and kind of contamination in a location are linked to the pollution sources that cause it, as well as local weather considerations.

Seasonal changes impact the propensity of pollutant buildup over the insulator's surface when the weather effect is stronger than the pollution source influence. In some circumstances, the pollution level's behavior is quite dynamic, with the maximum and lowest pollution levels occurring in the same year. The coastlines are typical examples[8]. Time-series models, regression models, artificial neural network (ANN) models [9], adaptive Neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS), and support vector machine (SVM) [10] models have all been proposed in the literature. The use of genetic algorithms allows for the definition of the arc constants, as well as the computation of the critical circumstances at the start of the pollution flashover process. A mathematical model has been developed that accurately mimics the experimental data [6]-[9].

In this paper, an LS-SVM regression with PSO and LS-SVM with GWO based model is proposed to estimate the critical flashover voltage of polluted insulators.

II. THE DATA SET AND THE MATHEMATICAL MODEL

Both experiments [11] [12] and an application of a mathematical model for calculating flashover voltage provided the data set for training and testing the technique. As stated in [7], the numerical model for the assessment of the flashover cycle of a contaminated insulator comprises of an incomplete bend crossing over a dry zone and the opposition of the contamination layer in series. The critical voltage U_c (in V) is the voltage applied across the insulator when a partial arc develops into a full arc and is given by the following equation [6]:

$$U_c = \frac{A}{n+1} \cdot (L + \pi \cdot n \cdot D_m \cdot F \cdot K) \cdot (\pi \cdot A \cdot D_m \cdot \sigma_s)^{\frac{-n}{n+1}}$$

Where L denotes the insulator creepage distance in centimeters, D_m the maximum diameter of the insulator disc in centimeters, and F the form factor.

$$F = \int_0^L \frac{l}{\pi D(l)} dl$$

The values of A and n are the arc constants. $A = 124.8$, $n = 0.409$ were calculated using a complicated optimization approach based on genetic algorithms [14]. It has been demonstrated experimentally that the value of a contaminated insulator's flashover voltage is not constant even under similar conditions. The kind of surface conductivity (σ_s) is given by the following type:

$$\sigma_s = (369.05 \cdot C + 0.42) \cdot 10^{-6}$$

Where C is the equivalent deposit density in (mg/cm²).

K is used to describe the pollution layer's resistance while taking into consideration the current concentration at the foot of the arc.

$$K = 1 + \frac{n+1}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot F \cdot n} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{L}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot R \cdot F}\right)$$

Where R is the radius of the arc foot (in cm) and may be calculated as follows:

$$R = 0.469 \cdot (\pi \cdot A \cdot D_m \cdot \sigma_s)^{1/(2 \cdot (n+1))}$$

III. ESTIMATION OF FLASHOVER VOLTAGE USING LSSVM-PSO AND LSSVM-GWO

A. Least-squares SVMs

As a modified variation of the SVM, the LSSV (Suykens and Vandewalle 1999) is a nonlinear extension of Vapnik's extended portrait approach. By transforming the SVM's inequality constraints into equality constraints, the quadratic optimization problem is turned into a linear system of equations. The error sum of squares is regarded as the training sample's loss function. The practice set is provided as $(x_i, y_i)_{i=1}^l \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}$ If x_i represents the input data, y_i represents the target data, and l is the number of samples. The regression function in feature space can be provided by:

$$f(x) = w^T \phi(x) + b$$

Where w is the weight vector, b is a bias term, and $\phi(x)$ is the kernel space mapping function from input to output space that transfers the input data points to a high-dimension featur space. The function optimization issue may be described using the structural risk minimization concept as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \min_{w,b,\xi} & \frac{1}{2} w^T w + \frac{1}{2} \gamma \sum_{i=1}^l \xi_i^2 \\ \text{s.t.} & y_i = w^T \phi(x_i) + b + \xi_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, l \end{cases}$$

Where γ denotes a regularization parameter and ξ_i denotes a slack variable. When the Lagrange technique is used to solve the optimization issue, the following results [6]:

$$L(w, b, \xi; \alpha) = \frac{1}{2} w^T w + \frac{1}{2} \gamma \sum_{i=1}^l \xi_i^2 - \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i (w^T \phi(x_i) + b + \xi_i - y_i)$$

Where an α_i is the Lagrange multiplier, the partial derivatives of L with respect to the primal variables w, b, ξ_i, γ must satisfy the following conditions:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial L}{\partial w} = 0 \rightarrow w = \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i \phi(x_i) \\ \frac{\partial L}{\partial b} = 0 \rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i = 0 \\ \frac{\partial L}{\partial \xi_i} = 0 \rightarrow \alpha_i = \gamma \xi_i \\ \frac{\partial L}{\partial \alpha_i} = 0 \rightarrow w^T \phi(x_i) + b + \xi_i - y_i = 0 \end{cases}$$

A linear equation may be derived using the Karush–Kuhn–Tucker optimal condition as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & \dots & 1 \\ 1 & K(x, x_i) + 1/\gamma & \dots & K(x, x_i) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 1 & K(x, x_i) & \dots & K(x, x_i) + 1/\gamma \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} b \\ \alpha_1 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha_l \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ y_1 \\ \vdots \\ y_l \end{bmatrix}$$

In which the kernel function $K(x, x_i) = \phi(x_i)^T \phi(x)$. This is a symmetric function satisfying the Mercer's theorem condition. The regression model may be built as follows:

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i K(x, x_i) + b$$

Because of its high nonlinear mapping capacity, the radial basic function (RBF) is utilized as the kernel function of the LSSVM model in this paper:

$$K(x, x_i) = \exp(-(x - x_i)^2 / (2\sigma))$$

where σ is the RBF function's width. The choice of two free parameters (regularization parameter γ and kernel parameter σ) in Eqs. directly influences the performance of the LSSVM model, as demonstrated by the LSSVM training problem.

B. Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO)

PSO is a stochastic optimisation technique introduced recently by Kennedy and Eberhart, which is inspired by social behavior of bird flocking and fish schooling. Similar to other evolutionary computation algorithms such as genetic algorithms, PSO is a population-based search method that exploits a population of individuals to probe promising region of the search space. In this context, the population is called swarm and the individuals are called particles. During the search process in the d -dimensional solution space, each particle (i.e., candidate solution) will adjust its flying velocity and position according to its own flying experience as well as the experiences of the other companion particles of the swarm [17].

The general principles for the PSO algorithm are stated as follows: Let us consider a swarm of size n . Each particle P_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ from the swarm is characterised by:

Its current position $D_i(k) \in \mathbb{R}^d$ which refers to a candidate solution of the optimisation problem at iteration k , its velocity $V_i(k) \in \mathbb{R}^d$, and the best position $P_{\text{best}_i}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^d$ that is identified during its past trajectory.

Let $G_{\text{best}_i}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^d$ be the best global position found over all trajectories that are travelled by the particles of the swarm. Each of n particles fly through the d -dimensional search space \mathbb{R}^d with a velocity $V_i(k)$, which is dynamically adjusted

according to its personal previous best solution $P_{\text{best}i}(k)$ and the previous global solution $G_{\text{best}i}(k)$ of the entire swarm. The velocity updates are Calculated as a linear combination of position and velocity vectors. The particles interact and move according to the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} V_i(k+1) &= w(k)V_i(k) + C_1R_1(K)(P_{\text{best}i}(k) - D_i(k)) \\ &\quad + C_2R_2(k)(G_{\text{best}i}(k) - D_i(k)) \\ D_i(k+1) &= D_i(k) + V_i(k+1) \end{aligned}$$

Where $V_i(k+1)$ is the velocity of (k+1)th iteration of ith individual, $V_i(k)$ is the velocity of kth iteration of ith individual, $w(k)$ is the inertial weight used as a trade-off between global and local exploration capabilities of the swarm. Small values of w result in more rapid convergence usually on a suboptimal position, while a too large value may prevent divergence. Typical implementations of the PSO adapt the value of w during the training stage, e.g., linearly decreasing it from 1.0 to near 0 over the execution. C_1 , C_2 are two acceleration constants regulating the relative velocities with respect to the best global and local positions, respectively. $R_1(\cdot)$ and $R_2(\cdot)$ are random variables that are drawn from a uniform distribution in the range [0,1] to provide a stochastic weighting of the different components participating in the particle velocity definition.

The inertia weight is set to the following equation:

$$w(k) = w_{\text{max}} - \frac{w_{\text{max}} - w_{\text{min}}}{k_{\text{max}}}k$$

Where w_{max} is the initial weight, w_{min} is the final weight, k_{max} is the maximum number of iterations or generation, and k is the current iteration number. This Eq allows the computation of the velocity at iteration $k+1$ for each particle in the swarm by combining linearly its current velocity (at iteration k) and the distances that separate the current particle position from its best previous position and the best global position, respectively. Typical convergence criteria are based on the iterative behaviour of the best value of the adopted fitness function(s) and/or simply on a user-defined maximum number of iterations.

C. Grey Wolf optimiser(GWO)

Mirjalili [16] recently proposed the GWO algorithm, which is motivated by the actual presence of a troop of grey wolves). The pack's wolves all adhere to a strict social controlling hierarchy. They are usually divided into four groups, with the leader wolf known as alpha (α) representing the primary responsible for making decisions about hunting, sleeping location, and time to wake, beta (β) considered as the appropriate candidate replacing alpha when the alpha passes away or becomes very old, delta (δ) known as the subordinate having several responsibilities: scouts, sentinels, elders, hunters, and caretakers, and omega (ω) representing the final grade of Grey Wolf. The major steps of Grey Wolf are as follows: hunting [16]

- Tracking, pursuing, and closing in on the prey.
- Pursue, encircle, and torment the target until it stops moving..
- Attack toward the prey

The wolf social hierarchy is theoretically structured with the fittest solution as alpha (α). As a result, The second- and third-best potential solutions are beta (*beta*) and delta (*delta*). The remaining answers are expected to be omega (ω). The following equations can be used to represent the encircling behavior:

$$D = |CX_p(t) - X(t)|$$

$$X(t+1) = X_p(t) - A \cdot D$$

where t is the current iteration, A and C are coefficient vectors, X_p signifies the prey's position vector, and X denotes the Grey Wolf's position vector. The values of A and C are computed as follows:

$$A = 2ar_1 - a$$

$$C = 2r_2$$

where a 's components are linearly lowered from 2 to 0 over iterations and r_1 , r_2 are random vectors in the range [0, 1]. The equations that describe the hunting process are as follows:

$$D\alpha = |C1X\alpha - X|, D\beta = |C2X\beta - X|, D\delta = |C3X\delta - X|$$

$$X_1 = X_\alpha \quad A_1D_\alpha \quad X_2 = X_\beta \quad A_1D_\beta \quad X_3 = X_\delta \quad A_1D_\delta$$

$$X(t + 1) = \frac{X_1 + X_2 + X_3}{3}$$

During the hunt, alpha, beta, and delta agents estimate the location of the prey, while other agents update their positions at random around the prey.

IV. ESTIMATION OF FLASHOVER VOLTAGE USING LSSVM-PSO AND LSSVM-GWO

A. LS-SVM parameter optimization using the PSO and GWO method

A variety of optimization techniques have been presented in the literature to determine the hyper-parameters of LS-SVMs to optimize their performance and deliver the lowest error or greatest accuracy rate. In the same vein, the PSO and GWO optimisation are used in this study to choose the RBF kernel parameters of the LS-SVM. These hyperparameters are the regularization parameter (γ) and the kernel parameters (σ^2).

The fitness function of each alternative solution is assessed using the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), which is expressed as:

$$RMSE = \left\{ \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n (y_{tes,k} - y_{pre,k})}{n} \right\}^{1/2}$$

Where N is the number of data patterns in the data set, $y_{pre,i}$ denotes the predicted value, and $y_{tes,i}$ denotes the testing value of one data point i.

B. Preprocessing of data

The aforementioned data were preprocessed in the same manner as in [6], with all input and output being normalised using linear normalisation, which ensures that superior value input characteristics do not overpower inferior value inputs, and so benefits for error reduction. As previously stated, the data used are taken from two sources: a mathematical model (140 estimated values) and the results of tests (28 real values).

The following are the major phases of the proposed hybrid model for LSSVM with PSO and LSSVM with GWO.

Step 1: Input data consists of training and testing datasets for five variable parameters (D, H, L, F, C).

Step 2: Data preprocessing : Using linear normalisation [15], each characteristic of the dataset may be scaled to the range [0, 1].

Step 3: Optimize the hyper-parameters Step 3.1: Initialization: Set the population of search agents, the maximum number of iterations, and the a, A, and C parameters.

The GWO method parameters selected for this work are N = 40 for the number of search agents and Max iter = 30 for the maximum number of iterations.

The parameters of the PSO algorithm: PSO learning factors C1 = C2 = 2, swarm size N = 20, inertia weight $w_{max} = 0.90$, $w_{min} = 0.20$, maximum number of iterations $k_{max} = 200$. The LSSVM searching parameters are set as $(\gamma) = [23, 223]$ and $(\sigma^2) = [2-8, 25]$, respectively.

The LS-SVM searching parameters are set to be $\gamma = [23, 223]$ and $\sigma^2 = [2-8, 25]$.

Step 3.2: Stopping criterion: Return to step 3.1 if the maximum number of iterations has not yet been achieved. Otherwise, proceed to the next substep.

Step 3.3: Select the best hyper-parameters: Finish the algorithm and provide the optimal hyper-parameters.

Step 4: Retrain the LS-SVM model: Retrain the LS-SVM model using the best (optimal) hyper-parameters obtained in step 3.

Step 5: Calculate the flashover voltage: After that, the flashover voltage is calculated

V. DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

A. GWO

The simulation results in pairs of (γ, σ^2) values that finally converge to the optimum values $\gamma = 3.64e+005$, $\sigma^2 = 1.351675$ as the number of generations increases (RMSE=0,01627) for LSSVM with GWO are shown in Fig.1 We can see from Fig.1 that the findings vary from generation to generation. The value of the performance criteria (RMSE) improves fast after the first generation and falls from 0.016292 to 0.01627 after 10 generations. It just takes 30 generations to obtain its ideal value (RMSE = 0.01627). Thus, Fig.2 depicts the contrast between the experimental data

and the estimated values for the test set, where 140 data points were utilized to train the model and 28 to test it. We see that the technique is well suited to the observed data.

Fig. 1. The evolution of the fitness function (RMSE) in relation to generations for (GWO).

Fig. 2. LSSVM-GWO model performance in testing.

B. PSO

The simulation yields pairs of (γ, σ^2) values that eventually converge to the optimal values $\gamma = 6.548516e+006$, $\sigma^2 = 2.2018$, as illustrated in Figs 3 and 4

as the number of generations grows (RMSE=0.01816), as illustrated in Fig 5, where it is clear that the method converges quickly to attain these values.

Fig. 3. Convergence of RBF parameter σ^2 .

Fig. 4. Regularization parameter γ convergence.

Fig. 5. The evolution of the fitness function (RMSE) in relation to generations for (PSO).

Thus, Fig. 6 depicts the contrast between the experimental data and the estimated values for the test set, where 140 data points were utilized to train the model and 28 to test it. We see that the technique is well suited to the observed data.

Fig.6. LSSVM-PSO model performance in testing

In this work, three distinct type validation indexes were employed to validate the performance of the LSSVM-PSO and LSSVM-GWO. These were the RMSE, the coefficient of determination (R^2), and the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE). The R^2 and MAPE may be calculated using the following equations:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n (y_{tes,k} - y_{pre,k})^2}{\sum_{k=1}^n (y_{tes,k} - \bar{y}_{tes,k})^2}$$

$$MAPE = 100\% \cdot \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n |y_{tes,k} - y_{pre,k}| / y_{tes,k}}{n}$$

where $y_{tes,k}$ is the average value of all data points. Furthermore, the validation indices RMSE, MAPE, and R^2 were compared to prior results published in the literature, as shown in table 1.

Table 1.

PERFORMANCE IS COMPARED IN TERMS OF STATISTICAL MODEL VALIDATION PARAMETERS.

MODEL	R^2_{tes}	$RMSE_{tes}$	$RMSE_{tr}$	$MAPE_{tes}$
LSSVM-PSO	0.9910	0.01816	0.0042	1.0975
LSSVM-GWO	0.9869	0.01627	0.0059	1.1074
LSSVM-ACO[17]	0.9915	0.01684	0.0039	1.1025
ANN	0.97	0.4929	0.0446	3.47
ANFIS[18]	0.988	0.4766	-	3.5158

According to Table 1, LSSVM-PSO and LSSVM-GWO are more strong in predicting flashover voltage on insulators is more than prior results reported in [18]. According to Table I, the suggested model has a lower RMSE for the test set as opposed to the LSSVM [15] based on Grid Search and the earlier results in [6]. Furthermore, the suggested model yields MAPE and R^2 values that are equivalent to the earlier values presented in [15] [9].

VI. CONCLUSION

This research looked at, an enhanced LSSVM according to the PSO and GWO algorithms was successfully a method for calculating the flashover voltage on contaminated insulators. The PSO and GWO Algorithms are employed to optimize

LSSVM parameters to produce an appropriate LSSVM model for the current situation.

When some geometric properties of the insulator are specified, the LSSVM-PSO and LSSVM-GWO with RBF kernel were trained to predict the critical flashover voltage. The findings reveal that the suggested model is more accurate in predicting flashover voltages of contaminated high voltage insulators.

Furthermore, various statistical measures, To evaluate the estimating performance of the developed model, metrics such as root mean square error (RMSE), coefficient of determination (R^2), and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), were employed. The findings reveal that the LSSVM-PSO and LSSVM-GWO models are more accurate and precise than the previously presented approach in estimating the flashover voltage (ANN, ANFIS and LS-SVM).

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